

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

Proposal No.: 848261

Deliverable D2.5 Creation of the Project Website

Deliverable No. D27 – WP2

Authors	Winfried Schlee (UHREG), Susanne Staudinger (UHREG)
Responsible of Deliverable	Winfried Schlee (UHREG)
Target Dissemination Level	Public
Status of the Document	Version 1

Table of contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Design and Registration Data	3
3	Website Structure	5
4	Main Pages	6
4.1	Homepage / Landing Page	6
4.2	About UNITI	8
4.3	Research	12
4.4	Public Release	14
4.5	Study and Contact	15
5	Target Audience	17
6	Statistics	17
7	Current and Future Developments	18

Table of Figures

Figure 1	Placeholder UNITI-website	3
Figure 2	Domain Info and Registration Data	4
Figure 3	First Draft of Website Structure	5
Figure 4	website Structure Jan/Feb 2020	5
Figures 5 and 5a	UNITI Landing Page / Homepage	6-7
Figure 6	Overview and Objectives	8
Figures 7 and 7a	Consortium	9
Figure 8	Organization and Management Structure	10
Figure 9	External Advisory Board	11
Figure 10 and 10a	Methodology	13
Figure 11	Publications	14
Figure 12	Press Review	14
Figure 13	Deliverables	15
Figure 14	Presentations at Conferences and Meetings	15
Figure 15	Tinnitus Clinics	16
Figure 16	Study Design	16
Figure 17	Registration	16
Figure 18	Contact Form	17

1 Introduction

This report – “D2.5 Creation of the project website” for “Task 8.1 Dissemination and communication plan and activities”, due on March 31, 2020 – describes the design and structure of the project website and gives an overview of the project activities so far related to the subtask “creation of the project website”, carried out by the University of Regensburg as a contribution to task 8.1 of the project “Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients”, UNITI (Grant-no. 848261).

2 Design and Registration Data

Initial preparations for design and construction of the UNITI website have already been made during the pre-project stage. After the grant agreement was signed by all project partners at the end of November 2019, a placeholder (static website) was online under <https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net> from December 6th, 2019 onwards; contact data concerning the clinical trial were added on December 17th, 2019 (Figure 1):

We are currently developing the webpage of the UNITI project
„Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients“
(Ref Nr. 848261).

You will find us here soon: internet: www.uniti.tinnitusresearch.net
twitter: @UNITI_Project
instagram: @UNITI_Project
facebook: @unitiproject

Patients, who are interested in participating in the clinical trial,
please send an email to
studie.uniti@tinnitusresearch.org

Figure 1 Placeholder UNITI-website

The current website is available since January 27th 2020 under <https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net>. Responsible for web-design, hosting and maintenance is JH&DM Developments UG, Ulm, Germany. The URL is a subdomain of tinnitusresearch.net, information about the domain and registration data are given on Figure 2:

WHOIS LOOKUP

tinnitusresearch.net is already registered*

Domain Name: TINNITUSRESEARCH.NET
Registry Domain ID: 1343127261_DOMAIN_NET-VRSN
Registrar WHOIS Server: whois.ionos.com
Registrar URL: <http://www.ionos.com>
Updated Date: 2019-11-28T08:41:04Z
Creation Date: 2007-11-27T19:20:06Z
Registry Expiry Date: 2020-11-27T19:20:06Z
Registrar: 1&1 IONOS SE
Registrar IANA ID: 83
Registrar Abuse Contact Email: abuse@ionos.com
Registrar Abuse Contact Phone: +1.6105601459
Domain Status: clientTransferProhibited <https://icann.org/epp#clientTransferProhibited>
Name Server: NS1123.UI-DNS.BIZ
Name Server: NS1123.UI-DNS.COM
Name Server: NS1123.UI-DNS.DE
Name Server: NS1123.UI-DNS.ORG
DNSSEC: unsigned
URL of the ICANN Whois Inaccuracy Complaint Form: <https://www.icann.org/wicf/>
>>> Last update of whois database: 2020-02-17T15:39:23Z <<<

Figure 2 Domain Info and Registration Data

3 Website Structure

A first draft of the website structure was presented at the UNITI kick-off-meeting, 15-17 January 2020 (Figure 3):

Project website

<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net>

Structure of the website:

- ✓ About UNITI
 - Overview
 - Workplan
 - Partners
 - Advisory Board
- ✓ Study
 - Deliverables
 - Scientific publications
- ✓ Media
 - Press releases
 - Newsletter
 - Brochure
 - Poster
 - Videos
- ✓ News / Outreach
- ✓ Contact

<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net> UNITI Kick-off meeting, Athens, January 2020 1

Figure 3 First Draft of Website Structure

After thorough discussion, the outreach and dissemination team around Ilias Trochidis, Winny Schlee, Axel Schiller and Susanne Staudinger eventually decided on the following preliminary structure (Figure 4):

Project website

<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net>

Structure of the website:

- ✓ Home
- ✓ About UNITI
 - Overview and Objectives
 - Methodology
 - Consortium
 - Organization and Management Structure
 - Advisory Board
- ✓ Research
 - Scientific Publications
 - UNITI Outreach Activities
- ✓ Public Release
 - Press Review
 - Deliverables
- ✓ Contact

<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net> UNITI Kick-off meeting, Athens, January 2020 1

Figure 4 website Structure Jan/Feb 2020

In the meantime the structure has been expanded, so that the website currently presents itself as follows

4 Main Pages

4.1 Homepage / Landing Page

The Landing page/homepage (Figures 5 and 5a) presents current news in the field of tinnitus (main frame), key facts about the UNITI project, upcoming events and links to the existing UNITI-accounts on Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, ResearchGate, LinkedIn and the Cordis database, in the frame on the right. Furthermore, tinnitus patients interested in participating in the planned UNITI study are invited to contact the project coordination by email for pre-registration.

Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients - UNITI

First UNITI Internal Database and App Meeting

03 March 2020

On February 14, 2020, the database and mobile app team of UNITI met in Würzburg. Myra Spiliopoulou, Miro Schleicher, Vishnu Unnikrishnan (OVGU Magdeburg), Eleftheria Velidou, ICCS Athens, Rüdiger Pryss and Carsten Vogel (University Hospital Wuerzburg) discussed first steps of the database as well as app unification issues. The Team was also joined by Ioannis Basdekis from the FORTH-ICS, Greece (via Skype). Additional meetings will follow soon.

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

On February 14, 2020, the database and mobile app team of UNITI met in Würzburg. Myra Spiliopoulou, Miro Schleicher, Vishnu Unnikrishnan (OVGU Magdeburg), Eleftheria Velidou, ICCS Athens, Rüdiger Pryss and Carsten Vogel (University Hospital Wuerzburg) discussed first steps of the database as well as app unification issues. The Team was also joined by Ioannis Basdekis from the FORTH-ICS, Greece (via Skype). Additional meetings will follow soon.

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

UNITI at Medical Valley EMN Erlangen

24 February 2020

On February 19, 2020, UNITI staff member Axel Schiller gladly followed the invitation of Medical Valley EMN e. V. Erlangen, a corporation of renowned experts in medical device design and regulation, to learn about the clinical evaluation of medical device software.

We greatly benefited, since the UNITI consortium, and especially our partners at the University of Würzburg (Prof Rüdiger Pryss), are already working intensively on the programming of new apps for tinnitus patients, to be used within the framework of our large randomised-controlled trial, starting early next year!

We are immensely grateful for this opportunity, and are very much looking forward to collaborating more with Medical Valley in the course of our pan-European project!

Workshop "Standard-compliant Software Development"

20 February 2020

The mobile apps for patient-centered research used in the study conducted in UNITI will be developed according to the principles of the Medizinproduktegesetz MPG and the new EU Medical Device Regulation MDR. At the invitation of the Chair of Clinical Epidemiology and Biometry of the Medical Faculty of the University of Würzburg, Winny Schlee and Axel Schiller from Regensburg took part in the training course "Normgerechte Softwareentwicklung im international regulierten Umfeld (DE, EU, USA)" (Standard-compliant software development in an internationally regulated environment (DE, EU; USA)), in which Marc Hofelder (IA? GmbH) member of the external UNITI Advisory Board, who presented the most important regulatory

Upcoming Events

- May 20** 20 May 2020
1st TRI Academy and pre-conference Tinnitus Workshop, Vancouver CA
- May 21** 21 May 2020 - 23 May 2020
TRI Tinnitus Conference "From Science to Succour", Vancouver, CA
- Sep 6** 6 Sep 2020 - 9 Sep 2020
XXXI Bárány Society Meeting, Madrid

Figures 5 and 5a UNITI Landing Page / Homepage

4.2 About UNITI

This menu contains an overview of the current status of tinnitus research, the presentation of the UNITI Consortium, the organizational and management structure and the Advisory Board. Under the sub-menu “Decision Support System DSS” we offer an open and expandable repository of experience, existing knowledge and data, which will finally lead to a decision support system regarding the best treatment option for specific patient groups (Figures 6-9):

UNITI Home About UNITI Research Public Release Study Contact

Overview and Objectives

Tinnitus is the perception of a phantom sound and the patient’s reaction to it. Although much progress has been made, tinnitus remains a scientific and clinical enigma of high prevalence and high economic burden. It affects more than 10% of the general population, whereas 1% of the population considers tinnitus their major health issue. Recent cohort studies show that tinnitus prevalence tends to increase over time and with older age. Assuming that there is no cure to be found, the prevalence estimates in Europe would double by 2050. A large variety of patient characteristics - including genotyping, aetiology, and phenotyping - are poorly understood, because integrated systems approaches are still missing to correlate patient’s characteristics to predict responses to combinatorial therapies. Although genetic causes of tinnitus have been neglected for decades, recent findings of genetic analysis in specific subgroups (gender and phenotype) have highlighted that bilateral tinnitus in men reached a heritability of 0.68. This heritability is close to autism, schizophrenia and Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder (ADHD). There is no current consensus on tinnitus treatment.

UNITI’s overall aim is to deliver a predictive computational model based on existing and longitudinal data attempting to address the question which treatment approach is optimal for a specific patient based on specific parameters. Clinical, epidemiological, medical, genetic and audiological data, including signals reflecting ear-brain communication, will be analysed from existing databases. Predictive factors for different patient groups will be extracted and their prognostic relevance will be tested in a randomized controlled trial (RCT) in which different groups of patients will undergo a combination of therapies targeting the auditory and central nervous systems.

The specific objectives of UNITI are:

1. To investigate genetic and blood biomarkers related to tinnitus.
2. To develop a unified database schema containing demographical, epidemiological, audiological, electrophysiological and medical history data, validated questionnaires, real time data collected from e/m-health applications and treatment progression features.
3. To develop an interventional mobile application, able to map tinnitus characteristics (e.g. frequency, intensity), produce individualized masking and music therapy (using filters in audio files uploaded by the patient) and record data in real time from each patient.
4. To conduct a multicentre Randomised Clinical Trial (RCT) with a combination of interventions, including Cognitive Behavioural Treatment (CBT), Sound therapy, Structured Counselling and Hearing Aid fitting.
5. To formulate the multilevel concept of the UNITI platform, by integrating all available parameters (epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, genetics and socioeconomic) , in a user-friendly Decision Support System (DSS) as a front-end, able to suggest specific examinations according to individual patient’s profile and optimal treatment strategy based on the sum of collected data.
6. To analyse the RCT results using sophisticated tools, taking into account detailed profiling of participants in correlation with results of Objectives 1 and 5.
7. Development of the first in-silico models, bridging cochlea and central auditory pathway with use of electrophysiological methods, which will provide auditory stimulus and collect responses up to the level of brainstem and cortex. The models will be utilised in order to improve personalised interventions, such as music/sound therapy.
8. To conduct a financial estimation analysis.

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

[f](#) [t](#) [i](#) [in](#) [R^g](#)

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

Upcoming Events

Figure 6 Overview and Objectives

Consortium

 Universitätsklinikum Regensburg	KLINIKUM DER UNIVERSITAET UHREG REGENSBURG (UHREG)
	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN (KUL)
 HELLENIC REPUBLIC National and Kapodistrian University of Athens EST. 1837	ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTRIAKO UOA PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON (UOA)
 UNIVERSITÄTSMEDIZIN BERLIN	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN CHA BERLIN (CHA)
	SERVICIO ANDALUZ DE SALUD (GRA)
	KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET (KI)
	OTTO-VON-GUERICKE-UNIVERSITAET MAG MAGDEBURG (MAG)
	UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL WUERZBURG
	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS

	UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL WUERZBURG
	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS
 ISTITUTO DI RICERCHE FARMACOLOGICHE MARIO NEGRI - IRCCS	ISTITUTO DI RICERCHE FARMACOLOGICHE MARIO NEGRI
	VILABS (CY) LTD
	SPHYNX TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS AG
	ZEINCRO

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations**
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

Upcoming Events

Patients

- **CORDIS database**

Upcoming Events

- May 20** 20 May 2020
1st TRI Academy and pre-conference Tinnitus Workshop, Vancouver CA
- May 21** 21 May 2020 - 23 May 2020
TRI Tinnitus Conference "From Science to Succour", Vancouver, CA
- Sep 6** 6 Sep 2020 - 9 Sep 2020
XXXI Bárány Society Meeting, Madrid

Figures 7 and 7a Consortium

Organization and Management Structure

Scientific Coordinator

PD Dr. Winfried Schlee, University Regensburg, Germany

Project Network Manager

Susanne Staudinger, University Hospital Regensburg, Germany

Dissemination Manager

Mr. Ilias Trochidis, ViLabs, Cyprus

Working Groups

WP1 Ethics

leader: Winfried Schlee, Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, University Regensburg, DE

WP2 Project Management

leader: Winfried Schlee, Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, University Regensburg, DE

WP3 Analysis of Existing Data

leader: Myra Spiliopoulou, Institute for Technical and Operational Information Systems ITI, University Magdeburg, DE

WP4 Harmonization of Technical Solutions

leader: Ruediger Pryss, Clinical Epidemiology and Biometry, University Hospital Wuerzburg, DE

WP5 Intelligent Data Analysis

leader: Eleftheria Vellidou, Institute of Communications and Computer Systems ICCS, University Athens, GR

WP6 Genetics

leader: Antonio Lopez-Escamez, Centre for Genomics and Oncology Genyo, Granada, ES

WP7 Randomized Clinical Trial

leader: Berthold Langguth, co-leader: Stefan Schoisswohl, Psychiatry, Center of Neuromodulation, University and University Hospital Regensburg, DE

WP8 Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation

leader: Ilias Trochidis, ViLabs, CY

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

Upcoming Events

May 20 May 2020

Figure 8 Organization and Management Structure

External Advisory Board

No	Name	Institution	Country
1	Prof. Dr. Ana Belén Elgoyhen	Instituto de Investigaciones en Ingeniería Genética y Biología Molecular, University of Buenos Aires	Argentina
2	Hazel Goedhart	TinnitusHub	UK
3	Prof. Dr. phil. Michael Koller	Center of Clinical Trials, University Hospital Regensburg	Germany
4	Prof. Dr. Raj Shekhawat	UCL Ear Institute London	UK
5	Holger Crump	Patient Organisation "Hast Du Töne" Bergisch-Gladbach	Germany
6	Dr. Ronny Hannemann	WS Audiology Erlangen	Germany
7	Marc Hofelder	LA2 GmbH Erlangen	Germany
8	Timon Oberholzer	WIA Ventures GmbH Gränichen	Switzerland

Figure 9 External Advisory Board

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

Upcoming Events

4.3 Research

The menu "Research" contains an overview about the methodology of the clinical study (Figure 10 and 10a) and a collection of scientific articles published during the project (

Figure 10 and 10a Methodology

Publications

The project started in January 2020. Here you will find all the Scientific Publications that UNITI consortium published during the project.

2020

Uli Nieman, Benjamin Boecking, Petra Brueggemann, Wilhelm Mebus, Birgit Mazurek, Myra Spiliopoulou:
Tinnitus related distress after multimodal treatment can be characterized using a key subset of baseline variables.

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?
 Study start is planned for Jan 2021.
 Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

f t i in R^g

Figure 11).

Methodology

UNITI can be perceived as a three-layered project.

In the **first layer**, existing clinical, epidemiological and genetic/blood biomarker data will be re-analysed with sophisticated analytic tools in order to identify factors correlated to specific treatment outcomes in the individual patient. Moreover, GRA and KI will perform additional analysis of their biobanks aiming towards the identification of candidate genes (rare and common variants), using Whole Exome Sequencing (WES) techniques. Additionally, an attempt to identify blood biomarkers specific to clinical subtypes, will be performed using a panel of the Proximity Extension Assay (PEA) method.

In the **second layer**, a large scale multicentre RCT will be conducted, with use of additional dimensions of analysis. Aim of this trial will not be only the comparison of tinnitus interventions' efficacy but also the validation of the treatment outcome predictions of the DSS.

The **third layer** will be the construction of an easy to use clinical DSS, which, based on the findings of the first two layers, will be able to identify the suitability of the particular patient for a list of the available interventions. More specifically, it will provide suggestion for specific examinations considered valuable for prediction of optimal treatment or combination of treatments, based on how good patient's profile fits to the identified patterns. DSS will be a component of the UNITI platform along with the in-silico model (OBJ7) and the mobile application (OBJ3).

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus

Patients

- **CORDIS database**

Upcoming Events

- May 20** 20 May 2020
1st TRI Academy and pre-conference Tinnitus Workshop, Vancouver CA
- May 21** 21 May 2020 - 23 May 2020
TRI Tinnitus Conference "From Science to Succour", Vancouver, CA
- Sep 6** 6 Sep 2020 - 9 Sep 2020
XXXI Bárány Society Meeting, Madrid

Figure 10 and 10a Methodology

Publications

The project started in January 2020. Here you will find all the Scientific Publications that UNITI consortium published during the project.
2020

	Uli Nieman, Benjamin Boecking, Petra Brueggemann, Wilhelm Mebus, Birgit Mazurek, Myra Spiliopoulou: Tinnitus related distress after multimodal treatment can be characterized using a key subset of baseline variables.
---	---

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?
Study start is planned for Jan 2021.
Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

[f](#) [t](#) [i](#) [in](#) [R^g](#)

Figure 11 Publications

4.4 Public Release

This section collects all press, radio and/or television contributions (if known) reporting on UNITI (Figure 12) as well as all submitted public deliverables (Figure 13). Presentations on UNITI content by scientists at conferences and meetings are listed under sub-menue Meetings and Conferences (Figure 13Figure 14):

UNITI Press Review

Here you can find a list of the various public outreach activities. Have fun watching our videos, reading articles, press releases and interviews.
Please click on the icons or the blue text to follow the link to the publication.

	Official Press release at the start of the project December 2019
---	---

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?
Study start is planned for Jan 2021.
Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

[f](#) [t](#) [i](#) [in](#) [R^g](#)

Figure 12 Press Review

Deliverables

Here is the list of all UNITI Public Deliverables:

	Deliverable name	Due date
	D2.1 Data Management Plan	M2 / February 2020
	D2.2 Report on Legal and Ethical Issues Monitoring	M15 / March 2021
	D2.3 Report on Gender and Equal Opportunities	M 39 / March 2023
	D2.5 Creation of the Project Website	M 3 / March 2020
	D3.4 UNITI Health socio-economic Impact Analysis	M21 / September 2021
	D4.2 Analysis of Medical Adherence on Existing m-health Data	M39 / March 2023
	D5.1 UNITI's Ensemble-based Prediction Models	M17 / May 2021
	D5.2 UNITI's In-Silico Model and DSS	M39 / March 2023
	D7.1 First Study Subject Approvals Package	M12 / December 2020
	D7.2 Midterm Recruitment Report	M27 / March 2022
	D7.3 Report on Status of Posting Results	M36 / December 2022
	D7.4 Final report on RCT, Dissemination, Communication and Community Building	M39 / March 2023
	D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan	M3 / March 2020
	D8.2 Exploitation Plan and Innovation Management Report	M27 / March 2022
	D8.3 Sustainability and Business Plans	M39 / March 2023

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

Figure 13 Deliverables

Presentations at Meetings, Conferences etc

Where

Date	Who	What	Where	Link/Downloads
Jan 21.-23.2020	Raj Shekhawat	Presentation of UNITI	UCL Ear Institute London UCL Tinnitus Master Class	https://www.ucl.ac.uk/ear/study/cpd-courses/coursepages/aamc-tinnitusandhyperacusis

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Figure 14 Presentations at Conferences and Meetings

4.5 Study and Contact

The menu study will present all relevant information about the planned clinical study, such as an overview of the participating clinical centres (Figure 15), the study design (Figure 16) and information about study registration (Figure 17).

Tinnitus Clinics

	Tinnitus Clinici at Universitaetsmedizin Berlin Charité	Prof. Dr. Birgit Mazurek
	Tinnituscenter Regensburg at University Hospital Regensburg	Prof. Dr. Berthold Langguth
	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Dept of Otolaryngology - Head & Neck Surgery	Prof. Dr. Thanos Bibas / Dr.Dimitris Kikidis
	Centre for Genomics and Oncological Research - Servicio Andaluz de Salud	Dr. Antonio Lopez-Escamez
	Department of Health Psychology at Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Prof. Dr. Johan Vlaeyen / Dr. Rilana Cima

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**

Figure 15 Tinnitus Clinics

Study Design

Within UNITI the largest clinical study on tinnitus will be conducted at 5 clinical centers in 4 countries (Belgium, Germany, Greece and Spain). The aim is to find out which patient groups benefit most from which treatment methods. The data from the clinical study will be combined with genetic data, medical and audiological examinations and already existing databases to develop a computer model that predicts the best possible therapy. The combination of several treatment methods will also be systematically tested for the first time.

The following treatments will be investigated in the study

- structured psychological counseling & psychoeducation (via App)
- Hearing aids or sound therapy (via App)
- Behavioural Therapy

and combinations thereof.

Detailed information on the study design will be provided shortly.

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Key Facts

Figure 16 Study Design

Registration

Patients who are interested in participating in the study can already contact us by e-mail

studie.uniti@tinnitusresearch.org

Please also let us know which of the above-mentioned study locations - Athens (Greece), Berlin (Germany), Granada (Spain), Leuven (Belgium) or Regensburg (Germany) is suitable for you.

We will add you to our study contact file and keep you informed about news concerning the UNITI study.

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?

Study start is planned for Jan 2021.

Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

Figure 17 Registration

Finally, under the menu Contact, a contact form opens, which can be used to send inquiries to the project coordination (Figure 18)

Contact us

From:

E-mail:

To:

Subject:

Message:

Send me a copy

UNITI Clinical Trial

Are you Tinnitus patient and interested in participating?
Study start is planned for Jan 2021.
Write an [Email](#)

Social Media

[f](#) [t](#) [i](#) [in](#) [R^g](#)

Key Facts

- **Coordinator:** Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg
- **Project Network Manager:** Susanne Staudinger, University Clinic Regensburg
- **13 coordinating partners, including 5 tinnitus centers**
- **Largest European Clinical Study on Tinnitus to Date**
- **Large European Network** of academic, clinical, industrial partners and self-help organisations
- **Goal:** Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients
- **CORDIS database**

Figure 18 Contact Form

5 Target Audience

On the one hand, the UNITI website is intended to address scientists who can follow the scientific basis of the project, the methodology, but also the results of the clinical study under the menu item Research. On the other hand, the open repository provides clinicians with information on the examination and treatment of tinnitus patients in their daily routine. Thirdly, tinnitus patients themselves will be specifically addressed. They will receive information on the planned clinical study and links to newer and latest literature on the subject.

6 Statistics

UNITI uses Google analytics to generate detailed statistics about the visitors of the website. The statistics will be recorded and presented in the appropriate sections (WP8) of UNITI's technical report during the two reporting periods (M18 and M39).

7 Current and Future Developments

During the Tinnitus Awareness Week (#Tinnitusweek2020, 5.-9. Feb 2020), four out of five institutions involved in the planned clinical study briefly presented their focus areas and teams to a broad public. In the course of the planning of the clinical study, further details about the institutions and their specific conditions will follow in order to make the process of study planning and later also the execution of the study as transparent as possible. A short presentation of the other UNITI partners is also conceivable.